

Title: Rapid Acceleration of Diagnostics: Underserved Populations (RADx-UP) Image Bank

Funding Source: National Institutes of Health, National Institute of Minority Health and Health Disparities

CONSENT

I, _____, consent to being photographed and/ or audio-recorded or provide a written statement to collect my personal COVID-19 story by _____ (Contractor or individual submitting photograph; see Photo Submission Guidelines document for more information) for use by the RADx-UP Coordination and Data Collection Center (CDCC), RADx-UP projects, or designees, and I agree to give RADx-UP CDCC the royalty-free, full permanent right to use my image and likeness in any media whatsoever, for the purpose of use, sharing, editing, publication, distribution, or republication by RADx-UP projects.

All photographers taking photographs must obtain a signed release form from any person appearing in the photo who is clearly recognizable in the photograph prior to taking the photographs. Crowd scenes where no single person is the dominant feature are exempt.

My signature confirms that I am 18 years of age or older and that I have read and signed this consent voluntarily, without intimidation, and I understand the potential use of the photographs and the consequences of such use. I allow the RADx-UP CDCC and RADx-UP projects to use my image and likeness in photograph(s), and written story, if provided, for publications, teleconferences, newsletters, brochures, or other such materials and in any and all other media, whether now known or not yet known. I will make no monetary or other claim against RADx-UP for the use of the photograph(s) or written story. You will be given a signed copy of this consent form.

Witness

Date

Signature

Date

Print Name of Witness

Print Name

Title: Rapid Acceleration of Diagnostics: Underserved Populations (RADx-UP) Image & Icon Bank

Contact Information for Compensation

Participant Name (Printed): _____

Participant Phone Number: _____

Participant Email: _____